

EOSC Support Office Austria: Visions, needs and requirements for research data and practices

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In 2015 the vision of a federated system of infrastructures supporting research by providing an open multi-disciplinary environment to publish, find and re-use data, tools and services led to the launch of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC). Against this background, bodies such as the [EOSC Association](#) on the European level and the [EOSC Support Office Austria](#) on the national one have been established.

Within this framework and since research has always been at the heart of EOSC, we are eliciting visions, needs and requirements for research data and practices from researchers who are located at public universities in Austria. Let's see what Susanne Reichl, professor of contemporary literature in English, has to say!

"I'd so much rather read a book than deal with data management"

Susanne Blumesberger (SB): Thank you for your time and let's start with our questions about data management. What does your work currently focus on?

Susanne Reichl (SR): My research in literary and cultural studies (in a wider sense) currently focuses on two things. The one is social media and literature. I'm working on a proposal for an FWF-project that is about the role that literature plays in social media and how this transforms our understanding of the role of literature in our society. The other thing is a project about reading literature for social change and social justice in the context of English language teaching. So two quite different things. One is more to do with books and what happens when people read books, and the other one is concerned with what is going on on social media that has to do with what young people read and

how they respond to what they read. I'm also co-editing an online open access journal called *Children's Literature and English Language Education*. I'm mentioning this because I'm using data differently in each case.

SB: And what are the things that drive your work and why?

SR: On the one hand, it's always the question what literature, what stories are good for in our

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society and in our world. Especially in a changing media landscape and in connection with teaching English at Austrian schools. So I'm

interested in what the status of literature in education is in the first place. What can literature do for us as readers, and for young people, who are in an important period in their lives, how they communicate about it, and what teachers can do. What drives me as a literature person is very much this idea that I'm not in an ivory tower. I'm trying to see its relevance in daily life.

SB: It's a nice picture. Thank you. And the next question is: what data are you working with?

SR: I've thought about this and I've done a kind of mind map, which has become quite big. My problem is that my data management seems so chaotic. I'm working with so many different varieties of data. Primary data can be books and they can be Kindle files. But they instantly become secondary data because I've also got my notes in my books and my Kindle files. In the social media project, primary data is everything that happens on social media and on websites like Goodreads that has to do with literature, so basically TikTok videos, YouTube videos, Insta Reels, but also screenshots of text-image combinations. For the social change and literature project, I've got audio data from focus groups, so transcribed audio data and the actual audio files. And then we also have numeric data because we did a survey with English teachers in Viennese schools. So we have the raw survey data, but then also the tables, the Excel files and all that. And I haven't even mentioned the secondary material that I'm reading yet, all those PDFs and sometimes photocopies and printouts, if it's slightly older material. They are all over the place. I'm keeping most of my data on u:cloud, but u:cloud is limited, and I also use notion and citavi. I have files in my email and on my Kindle, and I also use Dropbox to share files with my co-editors of the journal *Children's Literature in English Language Education*. It looks very organized at the beginning, but if you just put

lots of files on it, then you start losing control very easily. I also have a "Remarkable", a useful tool where you can write with your hand on a screen, and where I've put up lots of PDFs as well, because I can take notes as I'm reading through the PDFs, which is great for all kinds of uses. But then this is also somewhere in a cloud that belongs to "Remarkable". So as you can see, my data is all over the place. If I don't think about it, it's not a problem. But once I do it becomes scary. I've never backed up my Kindle files, and even though Amazon has no interest in deleting my cloud, I sometimes think, what do I do if my notes are gone? E-mails are a huge problem. You can sort them into folders, but you basically have to look at one after the other as they come in, no matter whether they are urgent or not. There's so much garbage in my inbox. I know that these smart inboxes exist, which sort things in advance for you and learn progressively. But because of data security, we cannot have them at the university.

SB: So let's go to the next question. What are the advantages and benefits of the software services you're using?

SR: I know u:cloud, how it works and everything. I don't have to worry much about it because I have someone in the background who I can ask if things break down. I can access it from everywhere, which is an advantage. I'm a very visual worker. I need to see where things are. I don't remember where they are if I don't see them.

SB: Now let me ask something about the trust in data quality. What are the key steps in defining or collecting or analyzing or interpreting or storing data in order to know they are and remain high in quality?

SR: I think findability is a major issue: I have to find it, so I have to quickly understand what's in it. Sharing is really important, too, but more than sharing, what I call mobility of data would be important, but it's probably the wrong term. Maybe it's more, like, adaptability? I want to be able to use my data very quickly for many different functions and formats. I want to be able to show it as it is, but then also maybe build it into a PowerPoint slide or send it to people or share it with students, put it on Moodle, use it on the remarkable and on notion, or email it. It's a kind of mobility across a number of platforms that I want for my data.

SB: So the next question is what constitutes the quality of high quality research data in your discipline or rather what practices ensure quality in data?

SR: I don't think my discipline is so different from other disciplines. I think it is crucial to contextualise the data, which is very important in cultural studies. That usually happens through the metadata, but in the case of social media that might not be enough. You can't analyse a single reel on Instagram and ignore the user profile or the comments, for instance. So how do you attach a screenshot to the video? Or with TikTok, you have a comments box and scroll through that, how can you store that? And of course social media changes so fast. Sometimes I want to go back to a particularly interesting post that I've bookmarked, but it's been taken off and might be gone forever. Obviously I should have recorded it, but I'm not used yet to doing screencasts yet, and they need a lot of space.

SB: When and why do you have trust in the quality of your research data?

SR: I've become very good at storing and finding PDFs or ebooks, but can't find other files as

easily. Often I have trust in the quality of the data itself, but not the quality of what I'm doing to it. So the quality of handling that data could be greatly improved. I keep telling students what they should be doing with their data systematically and then I'm not doing it myself because I'm too busy doing other things and don't find the time to systematise anything.

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SB: How do you judge the quality of research data of others, other disciplines or rather what are the criteria by which you judge it?

SR: I tend to think that most people are so much better at data management than I am. People who have learned how to do social studies research seem to be doing a lot better. I was never trained in doing research with data, and I noticed that my colleagues in literature have fewer issues with data: if you're reading books and secondary material most of the time, you probably don't worry quite as much about storage and findability as when you're doing social media research. And also: I'd so much rather read a book than deal with data management, so if I could have a full-time personal assistant who organises my data, I'd be happy.

SB: So I think we have a last question. When and why do you have trust in the quality of research data collected and shared by others?

SR: What I've done in terms of sharing data is mostly secondary material. I've done that in two or three projects where other people have

worked with or for me, and we've had a shared Citavi or Endnote for collecting sources. I very pragmatically decided to trust my research assistants, because I can't keep checking whether they're doing their job. I have to trust them. What would it take for me to trust someone else's data quality is probably to know that they're working by high standards. Is it data protected? Is it ethically okay? Is it contextualised? I don't use any other people's data on the whole. Recently I've tried to use more open source, copyright-free images. I've also stopped using pictures simply for the sake of having a picture. I also hardly show pictures of writers anymore in my classes, because I've found that students often read the text with a bias when they know that the author is coloured or very young. Sometimes I only tell them after they've read the text.

SB: That's a good idea.

SR: It makes them more aware of bias. I teach a picturebook seminar in the summer term. I've already scanned in a few picturebooks, because I don't expect my students to buy picture books that cost 15 or 16 euros and consist of just as many pages. I'm always a little uncertain of what you can do and what you can't do with regard to copyright.

SB: It's not so easy to find a way to learn it because there are so many different laws.

SR: I know. And social media is another nightmare, especially how to deal with all the legal and ethical challenges.

SB: Yes, there is still a lot to do in the field of research data management. Thank you very much for this interesting and nice conversation!

SR: It was very interesting for me, too. And I've got a list of things I have to find out about now.

Susanne Reichl is professor of contemporary literature in English at the Department of English and American Studies at the University of Vienna in Austria. She is also head of the interdisciplinary research platform #YouthMediaLife. She has published and taught in postcolonial literature, literature and reading pedagogy, and various aspects of contemporary British literature and cultural studies. Her research interests now focus on social media and literature, the role of literature in teacher education, and children's and young adult literature, especially time travel stories.